

HISTORY OF THE NAMANGAN REGION “MEMORY AND HONOR” MUSEUM

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***Annotation:** This article examines the history of the establishment, stages of development, exhibition structure, and socio-cultural significance of the Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum. It analyzes the museum’s exhibitions dedicated to participants of the Second World War, victims of repression, and achievements of the independence period. The formation of the museum’s activities, subsequent transformations, and its educational role in society are also scientifically considered.*

***Keywords:** Namangan, “Memory and Honor” Museum, victims of repression, Second World War, exhibition, memorial museum, cultural heritage, independence years, museology, moral education.*

Introduction: During the years of independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention has been paid to the study of national history, the perpetuation of ancestral memory, and the preservation of cultural heritage. In this process, memorial museums have emerged as important spiritual and educational centers. The Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum is one such significant cultural institution, serving to immortalize the memory of participants of the Second World War, victims of political repression, and individuals who contributed to the development of the Motherland during the years of independence. The establishment and activities of the museum are aimed not only at preserving historical memory but also at educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism.

In accordance with the Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, dated May 1, 2001, No. PD-2837, “On establishing the Day of Remembrance of Victims of Repression,” the Cabinet of Ministers adopted a resolution aimed at organizing the “Museum of the Memory of Victims of Repression” dedicated to perpetuating the memory of courageous compatriots who suffered during the years of the authoritarian regime [1]. The Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum is located at 40 Amir Temur Street, Namangan city. The museum building was constructed in the 1890s, specifically in 1893, by the Russian imperial official V. G. Bogaevskiy as a wedding gift for his daughter Maria. Initially, the building consisted of two rooms, and later four additional rooms were added [2]. Until 1975, it served as a residential house for various Russian families.

The Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum was officially established on May 9, 1975, in honor of the 30th anniversary of the victory in the Second World War, as the regional “House of Glory” [3]. The establishment of the museum was significantly contributed to by the Chairman of the Namangan City Executive Committee Melikhon Ibrokhimova, the Head of the Regional Defense Department Karimjon Isakov, and well-known local activists such as Tursunboy Ro‘zibaev and Tursunxuja Ahmadxujayev.

The museum consists of six exhibition halls. The first and second halls are dedicated to the compatriots of the Namangan region who showed bravery during the Second World War. These halls include a “Stella of World War II participants from Namangan region,” where photographs of local war heroes are displayed. The “Military Mobilization Stella” contains images of German prisoners of war, the defeat of Germany, German heavy artillery, and defenders of the Motherland. The “Front Assistance Stella” features photographs of women who contributed support to the front. The “Generous Uzbek” Stella displays images showing children of other nationalities living within Uzbek families.

The halls also present exhibits such as the 1942 Battle of Stalingrad map, letters sent by soldiers to their families from the front, a gas mask box used during the war, an aerial bomb, a machine gun ammunition belt, an automatic rifle, military epaulets, gloves, cigarette cases, spurs, grenades, a military belt, and soil from a battlefield brought by Khodjiev Sayfiddin.

The third hall is dedicated to the victims of political repression from the Namangan region. It reflects the words of Abdulla Qodiriy, considered the father of Uzbek novel writing and himself a victim of repression: “It is beneficial to revisit history and learn from it.” This section presents photographs of Namangan’s intellectuals and enlightened individuals who suffered repression, such as Lutfulla Alimo, Rafik Mumin, and G‘ofur Kosimov. The “Beautiful Memory” Stella provides detailed information about the “Memory and Honor Museum.”

The fourth hall is dedicated to the sons of the nation who sacrificed their lives for the defense of the Motherland during the years of independence. The fifth hall is dedicated to landscaping and beautification works carried out in Namangan region during the years of independence. The sixth hall is dedicated to the achievements of Namangan region during the years of independence.

The museum collection contains more than 22,000 exhibits, of which over 3,000 are displayed in the exhibition halls. The exhibition spaces are continuously enriched with new meaningful information and artifacts [4].

On 11 September 1975, by Resolution No. 99 of the Regional Party Committee and the Executive Committee of the Council of People’s Deputies, the museum was approved as a branch of the local history museum.

In April 2000, this “House of Glory” was renamed the Regional “Memory and Honor House” museum. Since 2011, it has been granted legal status and has functioned as an independent museum. According to the decision of the Namangan regional governor dated 18 July 2012 No. 220, five district museums Yangi qurbon,

Uychi, Turakurgon, Mingbuloq, and Chortoq as well as the Alixon “People’s Museums” were assigned as branches.

Over the years, the following directors have served in the museum: Altinbaev Rifkat (1975-1976), Dadabaev Zaki (1976-1982), Boyxonboev Turgun (1982-1983), Gayupov Isokjon (1983-2004), Yoqubjanov Ismatilla (2004,2005), Bakhriddinov Olimjon (2005-2007), Isokov Yunusxon (2007-2008), Mirzamakhmudova Farida (2008–present) [5]

Under the leadership of Altinbaev Rifkat, Dadabaev Zaki, and Gayupov Isokjon, exhibition halls such as “The Contribution of Namangan in the Second World War” and “Labor Heroes” were established and continuously enriched with new stands. Under Yokubjanov Ismatilla and Bakhriddinov Olimjon, the museum’s exposition was further expanded with new artifacts, and stands such as “Labor Heroes of Namangan” and “Fighters of Independence” were created. Various events and celebrations were regularly held.

Under Isokov Yunusxon, the “Internationalist Soldiers” exhibition hall and the “War Veterans of Namangan” stand were established. Mirzamakhmudova Farida has been working in the museum sector since 1996 and has served as the director of the Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum since 2008. She has contributed to the development of the museum’s material and technical base, documentation of the museum fund, and enrichment of collections with new exhibits. Between 2008 and 2015, she brought nearly 100 new exhibits to the museum. From 2008 to 2011, the museum operated as a branch of the regional local history museum, and since 2011 it has functioned as an independent institution after receiving legal status [2].

Due to independence, in our country, as the government’s attention to museums has increased, many new types of museums have been established. In particular, the opening of museums on historical themes has contributed to the development of historical knowledge among citizens of Uzbekistan, especially young people, and to

the formation of feelings of patriotism and love for the Motherland. As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, stated, this sacred feeling serves as a guiding star and a reliable compass; it shows the path of reforms and does not allow deviation from the intended goal. Knowledge of history makes a person spiritually rich, strong, and humane. Spirituality, as rightly emphasized by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov, becomes a powerful force when it is based on a deep understanding and knowledge of one's people's history, culture, and goals.

In our independent homeland, special attention is being paid to the restoration of national identity. In this regard, the objective study and promotion of the great contributions of our ancestors in history is of particular importance. Museums that once served only the ideology of the "Red Empire" during the Soviet period are now serving the development of national consciousness. In the independence period, special attention has been given to the development of museums. There are several reasons for this:

First, to restore national feelings that were suppressed and deliberately erased from our consciousness during the years of colonial rule;

Second, to revive forgotten history in order to strengthen national pride and national consciousness, and to truly understand our identity;

Third, to honor our ancestors properly and to educate the younger generation not only to be proud of their ancestors' names and heritage but also to become worthy successors of great traditions;

Fourth, to educate young people in deep respect for national values;

Fifth, to contribute spiritually to strengthening the moral resilience of society;

Sixth, to revive historical memory based on documentary sources and to provide aesthetic enrichment to people, etc.

In the "House of Memory and Honor" museum, meetings with war and labor veterans, as well as internationalist soldiers, have become a tradition.

The museum employed 14 staff members. In order to implement the Resolution No. 975 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 11 December 2017, Order No. 874 of the Ministry of Culture dated 14 December 2017, and Order No. 89 of the Namangan Regional Department of Culture dated 20 December 2017, a commission formed by the Namangan Regional Department of Culture conducted an inventory and review of museum objects, collections, and material-technical resources of museums scheduled for liquidation from 1 January 2018, including the Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum and its branches in Uychi, Chortok, Mingbulok, Yangiqurgon, and Turaqurgon districts [6]. As a result, 25,900 exhibits of the Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum, along with 6 horizontal display cases and 13 vertical vitrines, were transferred to the State Museum of History and Culture of Namangan Region.

In conclusion, during its period of activity, the Namangan Regional “Memory and Honor” Museum played an important role in illuminating the history of the people, honoring war and labor veterans, and immortalizing the memory of victims of repression. The museum’s exhibitions contributed to strengthening historical memory in society and educating the younger generation in respect for national values. Nevertheless, in later years, organizational and technical problems emerged, leading to the cessation of its activities. Overall, this museum occupies a significant place as an important spiritual and cultural institution in the history of museology in Uzbekistan.

References

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